

***In Silico* Toxicological Assessment CMR and Endocrine Disruptor properties of Stearic acid (Octadecanoic acid)**

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Executive summary

The objective of this study was to evaluate the toxicological potential of the Stearic acid (Octadecanoic acid; CAS: 57-11-4) by means of *in silico* tools.

Several *in silico* models including the (Q)SAR models of US EPA T.E.S.T. Version 5.1.2, Toxtree Version 3.1.0., Derek Nexus[®] Version 6.3.0; Nexus Version 2.6.0, Leadscope[®] Model Applier v.2023.0.0-15, ToxCast models v.2.3.0, VEGA Version 1.2.3 and the molecular docking model Endocrine Disruptome were used to address the genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, developmental/reproductive toxicity and endocrine disruptor activity endpoints.

In conclusion, the available predictions demonstrates that Stearic acid does not raise any concern as regard the genotoxic/mutagenic potential and for androgen and aromatase effects. Although, no robust conclusions can be drawn as regard the potential carcinogenicity and reproductive toxicity effects, a concern for endocrine disruption via estrogen and thyroid activity cannot be ruled out for Stearic acid.

1 Introduction

Stearic acid is a fatty acid component used in the prototype Safewax product which is intended to be used as fungicide on grapes by application of coatings onto plants. The purpose of this study is to obtain information on Stearic acid by means of *in silico* tools on the properties linked to cut-off criteria (CMR and ED properties).

1.1 The (Q)SAR models

1.1.1 US EPA T.E.S.T.

Toxicity estimation software tool (T.E.S.T) version 5.1.2 is a (Q)SAR developed by the US EPA providing several (Q)SAR methodologies. T.E.S.T. estimates the toxicity values and physical properties of organic chemicals based on the molecular structure of the organic chemical entered by the user. The methodologies include a hierarchical, the FDA, a single-model, group contribution, nearest neighbour and a mode of action method. The consensus method predicts toxicity by taking an average of the predicted toxicities from the available (Q)SAR methodologies. This model screens several endpoints with relevance for mammalian toxicology, including oral LD₅₀ in rats.

1.1.2 Toxtree

Toxtree (version 3.1.0), is a flexible, user-friendly, open-source application which is able to estimate toxic hazard by applying a decision tree approach. It was used in this assessment to estimate skin sensitisation, ocular and dermal irritation endpoints. Toxtree was commissioned by JRC Computational Toxicology and Modelling and developed by Ideacon Ltd (<http://ecb.jrc.it/qsar/qsar-tools>). Estimations of eye/skin irritation and corrosion potential are based on physicochemical property ranges (e.g., melting point, lipid solubility, water solubility or LogP) and structural rules. Skin sensitisation is assessed by identifying the mechanisms of toxic action for skin sensitisation using a SMARTS pattern-based approach, the alerts provide grouping into reactivity mode of action and do not predict skin sensitisation potential.

1.1.3 Leadscope® Model Applier

The Leadscope® Model Applier (Version 2023.0.0-15) provides (Q)SAR models and expert alerts to obtain decision support information on the potential toxicities of chemicals. All the (Q)SARs were constructed at the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) by the Division of Applied Regulatory Science (DARS), previously known as the Division of Drug Safety Research Staff. The prediction results for each model are presented as the “prediction” and the “positive prediction probability”. The prediction can be “Positive”, “Negative”, “Indeterminate” and “Not in Domain”. The outcome of a (Q)SAR prediction is given as the probability of being toxic on a scale of 0 to 1. The lower the probability value, the lower the potential toxicity of a test chemical. The Rodent carcinogenicity models (*in vivo*) are used by the FDA as supporting information for decision-making processes involved in the regulatory workflow. High-quality rodent carcinogenesis database (1682 compounds), covering a large number of structural alerts and characteristics of both genotoxic and non-genotoxic carcinogens, was reconstructed and used as a basis for constructing (Q)SAR models for predicting four rodent carcinogenicity study groups: male rat, female rat, male mouse, and female mouse carcinogenicity.

The external validation has been reported by FDA¹ in 2015 in which recommend using a positive probability cut-off of 0.4 for the maximum negative prediction and 0.6 for the minimum positive prediction, with probabilities of 0.4-0.6 representing equivocal or indeterminate predictions. The Reproductive Toxicity Suite models are intended to support regulatory decision-making processes. The RCA (Q)SAR models for prediction of reproductive toxicity in male and female rodents are based upon the DARS publications². As regard the endocrine activity suite models, the thyroid hormone perturbations effects are supported by the thyroperoxidase (TPO) inhibition, Sodium Iodide Symporter (NIS) Inhibition and Thyroid hormone receptor (TR) alpha and beta transactivation. These QSAR model were constructed using the Leadscope predictive data miner. A partial logistic regression models was developed with Leadscope defined features, and phys-chem properties as descriptors. The TPO inhibition model predicts the result of the Amplex Ultra Red-thyroperoxidase (AUR-TPO) assay. The results are classified as positive or negative based on the percent mean activity (chemicals with 20% maximal activity inhibition or greater were considered positive. Chemicals suspected of resulting in cytotoxicity were removed from the training set. Cytotoxicity was evaluated based on the selectivity parameter). The NIS inhibition model predicts the outcome of the NIS_RAIU_inhibition assay. The results are classified as positive or negative based on hitcalls and curve fitting parameters represented in the Integrated Chemical Environment (ICE) database with a training set of 340 structures while the TR models predict the TR alpha and beta transactivation call which is the most conservative result of the TOX21_TR_LUC_GH3_Agonist and TOX21_TR_LUC_GH3_Antagonist assays. The results are classified as positive or negative based on hitcalls and curve fitting parameters represented in the Integrated Chemical Environment (ICE) database with a training set of 6322 structures.

1.1.4 Derek® Nexus

Derek® Nexus (Derek Nexus version 6.3.0, Nexus version 2.6.0) is an expert, knowledge-based toxicology (Q)SAR software which gives accurate toxicity predictions for a variety of endpoints including mutagenicity chromosome damage, carcinogenicity, hepatotoxicity, teratogenicity, skin sensitisation, eye and skin irritation. Derek predictions include a measure of confidence in the prediction. Derek defines “probable” as meaning “there is at least one strong argument that the proposition is true and there are no arguments against it” and “plausible” as meaning “the weight of evidence supports the proposition”. In qualitative terms, “probable” is associated with greater confidence than “plausible”. “Equivocal” is defined as meaning that there is an equal weight of evidence for and against a proposition. This has been robustly demonstrated and published in Judson, P. N., Stalford, S. a., & Vessey, J. (2013). Assessing confidence in predictions made by knowledge-based systems. *Toxicology Research*, 2, 70 – 79. From the regulatory perspective, a prediction can be considered acceptable if it is based on the likelihood level equivocal or above (plausible, probable, certain). A likelihood level of at least equivocal was considered in this assessment.

¹ Kruhlik, N. L, Enhanced (Q)SAR Models for Prediction Rodent Carcinogenicity, SOT Meeting, San Diego, CA, 2015.

² Matthews E.J., *et al.* 2006: Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology 44:83-96 and Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology 44:97-110.

1.1.5 VEGA

VEGA application has been developed by Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri (Laboratory of Environmental Chemistry and Toxicology) and Kode srl. The official website of the project is <http://vega-qsar.eu>. VEGA version 1.2.3 allows to apply several (Q)SAR models to selected chemicals. Currently, there are 59 models implemented in VEGA, including CAESAR, a (Q)SAR developed by the EU for REACH. CAESAR is a statistically based model used in this document for the prediction of carcinogenicity and developmental toxicity. CAESAR models have been assessed according to the OECD principles for the validation of (Q)SAR. For the model validity a wide series of statistical checks are used and external tests are used to verify that the models perform correctly on new compounds. Other models incorporated into the VEGA platform were also used in addition to CAESAR models for mutagenicity, carcinogenicity and developmental toxicity endpoints.

1.1.6 CompTox Chemicals Dashboard

EPA researchers use rapid chemical screening (called high-throughput screening assays, HTS) to quickly and efficiently test thousands of chemicals. These data (including those from the ToxCast and Tox21 programs) are contained in the [InvitroDB](#) database. EPA's Toxicity Forecaster (ToxCast) is a collection of bioactivity screening data from heterogeneous assay platforms for thousands of chemicals of interest to the EPA. ToxCast is a multi-year effort launched in 2007 that uses a growing list of medium and high throughput *in vitro* screening assays to expose living cells, isolated proteins, or other biological molecules to chemicals. The cells or proteins are then screened for changes in biological activity that may suggest potential toxic effects ([ToxCast program](#)). Models considered within the CompTox Chemicals Dashboard (v.2.3.0), namely ToxCast Models are CERAPP Potency Level (From Literature), CERAPP Potency Level (Consensus)³ and ToxCast Pathway Model (AUC)⁴ for estrogen activity and COMPARA (Consensus)⁵ and ToxCast Pathway Model (AUC)⁶ for androgen activity.

1.1.7 Endocrine Disruptome

The online docking tool "Endocrine Disruptome"⁷ is recommended⁸ for the investigation of the endocrine disruption properties for screening purposes. The tool is an open source (<http://endocrinedisruptome.ki.si/>), user friendly and web based prediction tool and it uses molecular docking to predict binding of molecules to 14 different nuclear receptors: androgen receptor, estrogen receptors α and β , glucocorticoid receptor, liver X receptors α and β , mineralocorticoid receptor, peroxisome proliferator activated receptor α , β/δ and γ , progesterone receptor, retinoid X receptor α , thyroid receptor α and β . The 18 structures integrated in Endocrine Disruptome are carefully selected from 103 crystal structures. All structures and protocols are validated. Users

³ Mansouri, et al (2016) DOI: 10.1289/ehp.1510267

⁴ Browne, et al (2015) DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.5b02641

⁵ ResearchGate, 2017 DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.16791.78241

⁶ Kleinstreuer et al (2017) 10.1021/acs.chemrestox.6b00347

⁷ KOLŠEK, Katra, MAVRI, Janez, SOLLNER DOLENC, Marija, GOBEC, Stanislav, TURK, Samo Endocrine disruptome - an open source prediction tool for assessing endocrine disruption potential through nuclear receptor binding. Journal of chemical information and modeling, 2014, vol. 54, iss. 4, p. 1254-1267.

⁸ The tool is recommended for the investigation of the endocrine disruption properties of pesticides and biocides and it reported in the Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of the Regulation (EU) no. 528 and (EC) no. 1107/2009 (Appendix D).

are advised to consult the receptors' sub-pages to check the performance of each model. The most important parameter is area under the curve (AUC) under receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve. Models with higher AUC values should perform better⁹. Results are color coded and binned in 4 classes. Classes were divided in a way to more correctly predict negative results, *i.e.*, compounds that don't bind to receptors. Three thresholds were set per structure to enable a division to 4 probability binding classes: red, orange, yellow and green. For the threshold calculations sensitivity (SE) was used to obtain corresponding docking scores. Class "red" corresponds to $SE < 0.25$ and indicates high probability of binding, two intermediate classes "orange" ($0.25 < SE < 0.50$) and "yellow" ($0.50 < SE < 0.75$) indicate medium probability of binding, and class "green" ($SE > 0.75$) corresponds to low probability of binding.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Data input

The chemical structures of the test item and the reference substance were entered into the different (Q)SAR modelling tools by drawing the substance structure using the structure editor of the respective tool or by entering the SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System) notation.

2.2 Test molecule

Stearic acid was assessed for possible genotoxic potential, carcinogenicity, developmental/reproductive toxicity and endocrine disruptor activity. Identification parameters, the molecule and other structure information are shown below.

2.2.1 Stearic acid

Common name	Stearic acid
Substance structure	
IUPAC	Octadecanoic acid
CAS no.	57-11-4
Molecular formula	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂
Molecular weight	284.5 g/mol
SMILES canonical	CCCCCCCCCCCCCCCC(=O)O

⁹ <http://endocrinedisruptome.ki.si/FAQ.html> section FAQ: "How to interpret results?" and section "Targets" for receptor specific performance (score, sensitivity and specificity).

2.3 Software used

The following (Q)SAR software tools were used for each specific endpoint:

Endpoints	(Q)SAR models
Toxicology	
Mutagenicity	Derek Nexus, VEGA, Toxtree and US EPA T.E.S.T.
Carcinogenicity	Derek Nexus, Leadscope, VEGA and Toxtree
Reproductive and Developmental toxicity	Derek Nexus, Leadscope, US EPA T.E.S.T. and VEGA
Endocrine disrupting activity (ER binding, AR binding, thyroid and aromatase activity)	Derek Nexus, VEGA, ToxCast Models, Leadscope and Endocrine Disruptome

3 Results

The toxicological properties of Stearic Acid have been evaluated using *in silico* (Q)SAR modelling. The results are presented below.

3.1 Summary of the (Q)SAR predictions

3.1.1 Mutagenicity

(Q)SAR model	Stearic Acid
Mutagenicity	
Derek Nexus	
Mutagenicity models	Inactive for Mutagenicity <i>in vitro</i> (bacterium, <i>E. coli</i> , <i>S. typhimurium</i>)
VEGA	
Mutagenicity (Ames test) CONSENSUS model	Non-Mutagenic Mutagenic score: 0 Non-Mutagenic score: 1
Mutagenicity (Ames test) model (CAESAR)	Non-Mutagenic (Experimental) Into the Applicability Domain
Mutagenicity (Ames test) model (ISS)	Non-Mutagenic Into the Applicability Domain
Mutagenicity (Ames test) model (SarPy-IRFMN)	Non-Mutagenic (Experimental) Alerts for non-mutagenicity: SM143, SM157, SM163 and SM177 Into the Applicability Domain
Mutagenicity (Ames test) model (KNN-Read-Across)	Non-Mutagenic Into the Applicability Domain
Chromosomal aberration model (CORAL)	Inactive Could be out of the Applicability Domain
<i>In vitro</i> Micronucleus activity (IRFMN-VERMEER)	Inactive Inactive Alert: 32, 56, 57, 61, 72, 80, 88, 89 and 100 Into the Applicability Domain
<i>In vivo</i> Micronucleus activity (IRFMN)	Non-genotoxic Inactive Alert: 15 Into the Applicability Domain
T.E.S.T. EPA	
Mutagenicity Consensus method	Negative Predicted value: -0.07
Toxtree	
<i>In vitro</i> mutagenicity (Ames test) by ISS	No alerts for <i>S. typhimurium</i> mutagenicity
Structure alerts for the <i>in vivo</i> micronucleus assay in rodents	No alerts for the micronucleus assay (Class II)
DNA binding activity	No DNA binding alerts identified

Following the Derek Nexus predictions, Stearic acid is predicted to be inactive in the Ames test (bacterial mutation models). No additional alerts have been identified by any of the other available *in vivo* and *in vitro* genotoxicity models within Derek Nexus (*i.e.*, Chromosome damage *in vitro*, Chromosome damage *in vivo*, Mutagenicity *in vivo*, Non-specific genotoxicity *in vitro*, Non-specific genotoxicity *in vivo*, Photo-induced

chromosome damage *in vitro*, Photo-induced non-specific genotoxicity *in vitro*, Photo-induced non-specific genotoxicity *in vivo* and Photomutagenicity *in vitro*).

All Ames mutagenicity models implemented within VEGA (CAESAR, ISS, SarPy-IRFMN and KNN-Read-Across) predicted Stearic acid as non-Mutagenic. All four models are into the Applicability Domain of the respective models. The CONSENSUS model is based on prediction results from 4 models all in agreement. The mutagenic score of Stearic acid is 0 while the non-mutagenic score 1. Additionally, experimental negative data for mutagenicity is reported by CAESAR and SarPy-IRFMN models. The reliability of these Ames test models is thus considered high. VEGA models for chromosomal aberration and micronucleus (*in vivo* and *in vitro*) were also considered. The CORAL model for Chromosomal aberration, the *in vitro* Micronucleus activity IRFMN-VERMEER and the *in vivo* Micronucleus activity IRFMN predicted Stearic acid as inactive/non-genotoxic. No active alerts for mutagenicity have been identified by any of the three models. Despite CORAL model which could be out of the Applicability Domain, the *in vitro* and *in vivo* Micronucleus activity models, IRFMN-VERMEER and IRFMN, are into the respective Applicability Domain and thus considered of high reliability.

US T.E.S.T. EPA Consensus method predicted Stearic acid as Negative, with a predicted value of -0.07. The prediction is considered highly reliable since the Stearic acid structure is well represented within both the training and the external test set. Ten analogues have been identified with a similarity score between 0.65 to 0.99 in the external test set and between 0.90 to 0.98 for the internal training set. Additionally, concordance and specificity are high (equal to 1) for both sets within the Consensus method.

No structural alerts have been identified by the Toxtree model for Stearic acid by the *in vitro* mutagenicity (Ames test) by ISS, *in vivo* micronucleus assay in rodents and DNA binding activity. Although Toxtree prediction outcome may be considered of limited reliability because it does not consider the molecular size of the molecule, steric hindrance or further molecular properties but generally considers any substance containing the specific fragment for the analysed endpoint, the predictions are in line with the absence of alerts for mutagenicity from other applied models and thus considered moderately reliable and as supportive.

The available predictions clearly demonstrates that Stearic acid does not raise any concern as regard the genotoxic/mutagenic potential. Based on the *in silico* predictions a concern for mutagenicity is not foreseen for Stearic acid.

3.1.2 Carcinogenicity

(Q)SAR model	Stearic acid
Carcinogenicity	
Derek Nexus	
Carcinogenicity	No alerts identified
VEGA	
CAESAR	Non-Carcinogen P(Carcinogen): 0.23 P(NON-Carcinogen): 0.77 Could be out of the Applicability Domain
ISS	Non-Carcinogen No structural Alerts identified Outside of the Applicability Domain
IRFMN-ISSCAN-CGX	Possible Non-Carcinogen No alerts for carcinogenicity identified Could be out of the Applicability Domain
IRFMN-Antares	Possible Non-Carcinogen No alerts for carcinogenicity identified Could be out of the Applicability Domain
Toxtree	
Carcinogenicity (genotox and nongenotox) and mutagenicity rulebase by ISS	Negative for genotoxic carcinogenicity Negative for nongenotoxic carcinogenicity
Leadscope	
carc female mouse	Negative Probability score: 0.114
carc female rat	Negative Probability score: 0.041
carc male mouse	Negative Probability score: 0.203
carc male rat	Positive Probability score: 0.506

The knowledge-based Derek Nexus (Q)SAR model identified no alerts for carcinogenicity for Stearic acid.

Following the models implemented in VEGA, Stearic acid is predicted as non-carcinogen by the CAESAR and by ISS models. Both predictions can be out and are outside of the Applicability Domain of the respective model. For CAESAR the probability value for non-carcinogenicity is above the cut off value of 0.5 (0.77). No alerts have been found by ISS model. For both models, although strongly similar compounds with known experimental value in the training set have been found, the prediction concordance (*i.e.*, most similar molecule

prediction disagree with the experimental value) and the accuracy are low. IRFMN-ISSCAN-CGX and IRFMN-Antares models predicted Stearic acid as possible non-carcinogen. No alerts for carcinogenicity were identified for Stearic acid. However, both predictions could be outside of the Applicability Domain and thus considered of limited reliability.

No structural alerts have been identified by the Toxtree model for Stearic acid by the Carcinogenicity (genotox and nongenotox) and mutagenicity rulebase by ISS. Although Toxtree prediction outcome may be considered of limited reliability because it does not consider the molecular size of the molecule, steric hindrance or further molecular properties but generally considers any substance containing the specific fragment for the analysed endpoint, the predictions are in line with the absence of alerts from other applied models for carcinogenicity and thus considered moderately reliable and as supportive.

Four additional Leadscope statistical models were run for the carcinogenicity endpoint. Three out of four models reported Stearic acid as negative with a probability score of 0.114, 0.041 and 0.203, respectively, indicating no concern for carcinogenicity in female mouse and rat and in female rat. Only one model, carc male rat, predict Stearic acid as positive for carcinogenicity in male rat. However, the probability score is just above the model's cut off value of 0.5 (*i.e.*, 0.506). However, based on the FDA external validation report (see section 1.1.3), the minimum recommended cut off for positive prediction should be 0.6, meaning that a score between 0.4 and 0.6 represent an equivocal or indeterminate prediction. Additionally, despite the input structure seems to be well represented among the Leadscope carcinogenicity models (6 – 9 model feature counts), only two analogues have been found within the training set of the carc male rat having a similarity score ≥ 0.8 while the other compounds have very low similarity (≤ 0.6 to 0.3). Based on these considerations, the Leadscope carc male rat prediction is considered equivocal and of limited reliability. However, the Leadscope predictions on female rat and mice and on male mice are considered of moderate reliability since also in line with the outcomes of the additional applied models.

Overall, the applied *in silico* tools are align, except for one Leadscope model (Leadscope carc male rat: equivocal outcome) and support no concern as regard the carcinogenicity potential of Stearic acid. However, no clear and robust conclusions can be drawn as regard the potential carcinogenicity effects of Stearic acid in the absence of experimental available data.

3.1.3 Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity

(Q)SAR model	Stearic acid
Developmental Toxicity	
Derek Nexus	
Developmental toxicity / teratogenicity	No alert found
T.E.S.T. EPA	
Developmental Toxicity Consensus method	Developmental Toxicant (predicted value: 0.65)
VEGA	
Developmental Toxicity (CAESAR)	Non-Toxicant Could be out of the Applicability Domain
Developmental/Reproductive Toxicity (PG)	Non-Toxicant Outside of the Applicability Domain
Leadscope	
Repro Female Mouse	Not in Domain Probability score: 0.441
Repro Female Rat	Negative Probability score: 0.111
Repro Male Mouse	Not in Domain Probability score: 0.619
Repro Male Rat	Not in Domain Probability score: 0.506
Repro Mouse Sperm	Positive Probability score: 0.922
Repro Rat Sperm	Negative Probability score: 0.473

Derek Nexus predictions resulted in the absence of alerts with relevance to developmental toxicity and teratogenicity for Stearic acid indicating the absence of concern for these endpoints for the structure.

T.E.S.T. EPA Consensus method predicted Stearic acid as Developmental Toxicant with a score of 0.65. However, the structure is poorly represented within both the training and the external test set (one similar structure within the external test set and two similar structures within the training set). For the training set, both analogues are experimentally negative and only one of them has a similarity higher than 0.6. Within the external test set, the only analogue found is experimentally positive but with a similarity of only 0.50. Additionally, the Consensus method prediction is based only on two out of three models since for the Nearest neighbor method insufficient chemicals exceeding the minimum similarity coefficient were found and therefore no prediction

was performed by this method. Overall, based on the poor representation of the structure within T.E.S.T. EPA model for developmental toxicity, the prediction is considered of low reliability.

Stearic acid is predicted as Non-Toxicant for Developmental/Reproductive toxicity by the CAESAR and PG model within VEGA. However, the Applicability Domain index is 0.779 and 0 for the two models respectively. Thus, the predictions could be outside and are out of the respective Applicability Domain. Even if strongly similar compounds with known experimental value in the training set have been found, accuracy and atom centered fragments similarity check of the models are good, the model's concordance is not adequate (*i.e.*, similar molecules found in the training set have experimental values that disagree with the predicted value) and thus not in Domain. Therefore, VEGA predictions for Developmental/Reproductive toxicity are considered of moderate-low reliability.

Additional Leadscope statistical models were run for the reproductive toxicity endpoint. Three out of six models reported Stearic acid as not in Domain¹⁰ with a probability score of 0.441, 0.619 and 0.506 for Repro Female Mouse, Repro Male Mouse and Repro Male Rat, respectively. Despite their inapplicability Domain, the predicted probability scores are borderline since very close to the cut off value of 0.5 and with very limited reliability since not enough features or analogues have been found for Stearic acid. The Repro Female Rat indicates no concern for reproductive toxicity in rat female with a clear probability score of 0.111. However, only one model feature count has been reported and the most similar molecules (similarity of 0.8) within the training set are predicted to be not in Domain although experimentally negative. Similarly, the Repro Rat Sperm model predict the substance as negative with a score slightly below the cut-off value of 0.5. Although some features were found in the molecules within the training set, the analogues similarity is limited (only one analogue has similarity of 0.8 and the remaining have a similarity score ≤ 0.47). As regard the Repro Mouse Sperm model, Stearic acid was predicted to be positive with a high probability score (0.922). A good number of model feature have been reported (*i.e.*, 14) although only 3 analogues with very low similarity score (< 0.5) have been found within the training set. Overall, based on the detailed model evaluation, the Leadscope models' outcomes are considered of low reliability independently of their predicted result.

The applied *in silico* tools are align and support no concern as regard the Developmental/Reproductive toxicity potential of Stearic acid except for the Repro Mouse Sperm model and T.E.S.T. EPA Consensus. Based on the limited prediction reliability outcome, no robust conclusions can be drawn as regard the potential reproductive/developmental toxicity effects of Stearic acid.

¹⁰ Leadscope uses two parameters to guide the applicability of model domain: having at least one structural feature defined in the model in addition to all the property descriptors; 2) having at least one chemical in a training neighborhood with at least 30% global similarity to the test structure.

3.1.4 Endocrine disruptor activity

3.1.4.1 Estrogen activity

(Q)SAR model	Stearic acid
Endocrine disruption activity - Estrogen	
Derek Nexus	
Oestrogen receptor modulation	No alert identified
Oestrogenicity	
VEGA	
Estrogen Receptor-mediated effect (IRFMN-CERAPP)	Non-active Alerts for non-activity: 1 Alerts for possible non-activity: 2 and 9 Into the Applicability Domain
Estrogen Receptor Relative Binding Affinity model (IRFMN)	Active Outside of the Applicability Domain
Bioactivity – ToxCast (CompTox Chemicals Dashboard)	
CERAPP Potency Level (From Literature) -Estrogen	Agonist: Inactive Antagonist: very weak Binding: very weak
CERAPP Potency Level (Consensus) – Estrogen	Agonist: 0 Antagonist: 1 Binding: 1
ToxCast Pathway Model (AUC) - Estrogen	Agonist: 0.248 Antagonist: 0 Binding: -
Endocrine Disruptome	
Estrogen receptor alpha (ER α)	ER α (agonist): -6.3 Low binding probability ER α (antagonist): -6.1 Low binding probability
Estrogen receptor beta (ER β)	ER β (agonist): -6.4 Low binding probability ER β (antagonist): -6.1 Low binding probability

The Derek Nexus predictions resulted in the absence of alerts with relevance to Oestrogen receptor modulation and Oestrogenicity for Stearic acid.

No experimental data on Stearic acid have been reported by the estrogen models implemented in VEGA: Estrogen Receptor-mediated effect (IRFMN-CERAPP) and Estrogen Receptor Relative Binding Affinity model (IRFMN). The first model predicts the substance as non-active identifying the presence of one alert for non-activity and two alerts for possible non-activity. Moreover, Stearic acid is into the Applicability Domain of the model and thus considered reliable. On the other hand, opposite prediction outcome is reported by the IRFMN model, *i.e.*, active for estrogen receptor binding. The model is however outside of the Applicability Domain of the model since accuracy and concordance for prediction of similar molecules is not adequate and only moderately similar compounds with known experimental value in the training set have been found in the training set. On these bases the IRFMN prediction is considered not reliable.

Additional positive outcomes are however reported by the models available within the CompTox Chemicals Dashboard. CERAPP potency Level predict Stearic acid as positive for antagonist and binding (Consensus score of 1 and Literature as very weak, *i.e.*, activity concentration between 20 and 800 μM ¹¹). ToxCast CERAPP model is based on the combination of 18 diverse ER HTS assay screening tests four of which resulted positive when tested with Stearic acid (as previously described in section 4.2.5 of the SafeWax project no: 101099462 - assays: NVS_NR_hER; ACEA_ER_80hr; ATG_ERE_CIS and ATG_ERa_TRANS). Moreover, ToxCast Pathway Model (AUC)¹² reported Agonist value of 0.248 and thus resulting in a positive prediction for estrogen activity according to the model developer (ToxCast ER agonist scores ≥ 0.1 are considered positive; scores of $0.1 > \text{AUC} > 0$ are considered inconclusive¹³; $\text{AUC} = 0$ are considered inactive).

On the other hand, in the investigation of the ER binding via the docking model Endocrine Disruptome, the model predicted low binding probability ($\text{SE} > 0.75$, green category) for ER α and β agonist and antagonist for Stearic acid, with a low binding probability value, expressed as the area under the curve (AUC, under receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve of the model) equal to -6.3 and -6.4 for ER α and β agonist and -6.1 for both ER α and β antagonist binding.

Overall, based on the controversial *in silico* predictions and considering the available *in vitro* positive assays from ToxCast a concern for endocrine disruptor activity via potential agonist and antagonist estrogen effects cannot be excluded for Stearic acid. However, no robust conclusions can be drawn based on the lack of experimental reproductive toxicity, short-term and/or long-term toxicity studies.

¹¹ Mansouri, et al (2016) DOI: 10.1289/ehp.1510267

¹² Browne P., et al (2015) DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.5b02641

¹³ Model scores of $0.1 > \text{AUC} > 0$ were considered inconclusive for this validation because these chemicals were active in only one or two ToxCast ER assays and activity was limited to the highest concentrations tested.

3.1.4.2 Androgen activity

(Q)SAR model	Stearic acid
Endocrine disruption activity – Androgen	
Derek Nexus	
Androgen receptor modulation	No alert identified
VEGA	
Androgen Receptor-mediated effect (IRFMN-COMPARA)	Experimentally Non-active Inactive alert: 118 Into the Applicability Domain
Bioactivity – ToxCast (CompTox Chemicals Dashboard)	
ToxCast Pathway Model (AUC) - Androgen	Agonist: 0 Antagonist: 0 Binding: -
COMPARA (Consensus) - Androgen	Agonist: 0 Antagonist: 0 Binding: 0
Endocrine Disruptome	
Androgen receptor (AR)	AR (agonist): -6.2 Low binding probability AR (antagonist): -6.2 Low-mid binding probability

The Derek Nexus predictions resulted in the absence of alerts with relevance to Androgen receptor modulation for Stearic acid.

Experimental data on Stearic acid have been reported by Androgen Receptor-mediated effect (IRFMN-COMPARA) model implemented in VEGA. The molecule is thus considered within the Applicability domain of the model. Additionally, an inactive alert (no. 118) has been fired for Stearic acid. The prediction outcome is therefore considered reliable.

Moreover, negative predictions are also reported by the models available on CompTox Chemicals Dashboard. Both ToxCast Pathway Model (AUC¹⁴) and COMPARA (Consensus) for Androgen receptor reported inactivity for binding and inactivity potential for agonist or antagonist activity (score equal to 0, based on the inactivity in 17 other cell-based AR assays and only active in one antagonist cell-based AR assay, *i.e.*, the ACEA_AR_antagonist_80hr).

Additionally, the docking model Endocrine Disruptome predicted low binding probability (SE > 0.75, green category) for AR agonism and antagonism for Stearic acid, with a binding probability value, expressed as the

¹⁴ AUC ≥ 0.1 considered to be positive. AUC values of 0.001 ≥ AUC > 0.1 indicate very weak potential activity and considered inconclusive. AUC values < 0.001 (set equal to zero) considered negative.

area under the curve (AUC, under receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve of the model) equal to -6.2 for AR agonism and AR antagonism binding.

The available predictions clearly demonstrates that Stearic acid does not raise any concern as regard the endocrine disruption potential via androgen activity. Based on the *in silico* predictions a concern for endocrine disruption potential via androgen activity is not foreseen for Stearic acid.

3.1.4.3 Thyroid activity

Q)SAR model	Stearic acid
Endocrine disruption activity – Thyroid	
VEGA	
Thyroid Receptor Alpha effect (NRMEA)	Inactive Into the Applicability Domain of the model
Thyroid Receptor Beta effect (NRMEA)	Inactive Into the Applicability Domain of the model
Thyroperoxidase Inhibitory Activity (OBERON)	Inactive (Experimental) Into the Applicability Domain of the model
Endocrine Disruptome	
Thyroid hormone receptor alpha (TR α)	-7 Low binding probability
Thyroid hormone receptor beta (TR β)	-6.9 Low binding probability
Leadscope	
NIS Inhibition	Negative Probability score: 0.141
TPO Inhibition	Negative (Experimental) Probability score: 0.033
TR Binding and Transactivation	Positive (Experimentally Positive) Probability score: 0.616

No experimental data on Stearic acid have been reported by the models implemented in VEGA as regard Thyroid activity. However, both the Thyroid Receptor Alpha effect (NRMEA) and Thyroid Receptor Beta effect (NRMEA) predicted Stearic acid as inactive. Similarly, the Thyroperoxidase Inhibitory Activity (OBERON) reported the molecule to be inactive. All three models are into the Applicability Domain of the respective models. Since the models within VEGA fulfil the Applicability Domain rules (Into the AD), the prediction outcomes are considered reliable. Additionally, negative experimental data are available for TPO (Thyroperoxidase) inhibition according to OBERON model.

Additionally, the docking model Endocrine Disruptome predicted low binding probability ($SE > 0.75$, green category) for Thyroid hormone receptor alpha and beta (TR α and β) for Stearic acid, with a binding probability value, expressed as the area under the curve (AUC, under receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve of the model) equal to -7 and -6.9 for both Thyroid hormone receptor alpha and beta.

Leadscope statistical model predicted Stearic acid as negative with a probability score of 0.141 for NIS inhibition. Stearic acid is poorly represented within the training dataset. Only three analogues (all containing fluorine atoms) have been found within the training dataset and have a similarity score of 0.4. However, the prediction probability is very low due to the presence of negative features. This prediction is considered of moderate reliability. For the TPO inhibition model, Stearic acid is well represented within the training set. The molecule as well as eleven chemicals with a similarity score between 0.8 to 1, have been reported to be experimentally negative for TPO inhibition within the internal training set. Moreover, the features contribution supports a negative prediction via a calculated score of 0.033. On these bases the prediction is considered reliable. The TR Binding and Transactivation model give however a positive prediction for Stearic acid with a probability score of 0.616. The prediction is considered reliable since experimental data on Stearic acid are available within the internal training dataset of the model. Thus, based on the reported experimental data, a concern for TR binding and transactivation is foreseen.

The available predictions indicate that Stearic acid does not raise concern as regard the endocrine disruption potential on the thyroid via NIS and TPO inhibition mode of action. However, based on the available experimental data reported by Leadscope, a concern for thyroid effects via binding to the thyroid receptor and/or transactivation is foreseen for Stearic acid.

3.1.4.4 Steroidogenesis activity

(Q)SAR model	Stearic acid
<i>Endocrine disruption activity – Steroidogenesis</i>	
VEGA	
Aromatase activity model (IRFMN)	<p>Inactive (Experimental) Probability(Active Agonist): 0.024 Probability(Active Antagonist): 0.038 Probability(Inactive): 0.938 Into the Applicability Domain</p>
Aromatase activity model (TOX21)	<p>Inactive Alerts for inactivity: SA7 and SA18 Alerts for agonist activity: SA4 Outside the Applicability Domain</p>

Both the Aromatase activity models (IRFMN and TOX21) predicted Stearic acid as inactive. Additionally, an experimental data is available within the training dataset on Stearic acid indicating that the molecule is inactive for aromatase activity (IRFMN model). Based on the available experimental value and the model prediction (inactive probability of 0.938), the prediction is into the Applicability Domain and thus considered robust and

reliable. Despite the TOX21 model predict Stearic acid as inactive, the model is outside the Applicability Domain of the model. Alerts for inactivity and for agonist activity have been identified by the model. Additionally, only moderately similar compounds with known experimental value in the training set have been found and the concordance within TOX21 model is not adequate (*i.e.*, similar molecules found in the training set have experimental values that disagree with the predicted value). On this basis, TOX21 model is considered of low reliability.

The available predictions clearly demonstrates that Stearic acid does not raise concern as regard the aromatase activity potential. Based on the *in silico* predictions and the available reported negative experimental data, concern for aromatase activity is not expected for Stearic acid.

4 Overall conclusion

The objective of this study was to evaluate the genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, developmental/reproductive toxicity and endocrine disruptor activity properties (CMR and ED properties) of Stearic acid by means of *in silico* predictions.

Based on the *in silico* predictions from Derek Nexus, Toxtree and US EPA T.E.S.T. as well as the VEGA predictions and experimental data (Ames test) reported, no concern for mutagenicity is foreseen for Stearic acid.

The available (Q)SAR results support no concern as regard the carcinogenicity and reproductive/developmental toxicity of Stearic acid. However, due to the limited prediction reliability, no clear and robust conclusions can be drawn as regard these endpoints.

Stearic acid is considered of no concern for the androgen and aromatase activities since VEGA, ToxCast and Endocrine Disruptome suggested no activity for these endpoints. However, based on the positive prediction outcomes and the available *in vitro* positive assays (ToxCast) on ER and the Leadscope Binding and Transactivation outcome for TR, a concern for endocrine disruptor effects via agonist/antagonist estrogen receptor as well as thyroid perturbation cannot be excluded.

In conclusion, the available predictions demonstrates that Stearic acid does not raise any concern as regard the genotoxic/mutagenic potential and for androgen and aromatase effects. Although, no robust conclusions can be drawn as regard the potential carcinogenicity and reproductive toxicity effects, a concern for endocrine disruption via estrogen and thyroid activity cannot be ruled out for Stearic acid.

Appendices

- Appendix 1** US EPA T.E.S.T. predictions report
- Appendix 2** Derek Nexus (Q)SAR models report
- Appendix 3** Toxtree (Q)SAR models report
- Appendix 4** (Q)SAR models within VEGA report
- Appendix 5** ToxCast Models report
- Appendix 6** Docking with Endocrine Disruptome
- Appendix 7** Leadscope models report